

Interfacial engineering from material to solvent: A mechanistic understanding on stabilizing α -formamidinium lead triiodide perovskite photovoltaics

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ABSTRACT

Formamidinium lead triiodide (FAPbI₃) has recently been considered as the most promising candidate to achieve highly efficient perovskite solar cells (PSCs). Excitingly, the state-of-the-art highest efficiency of FAPbI₃ based PSCs have reached over 25%. However, their device stability still lags behind other compositions of mixed-cation and mixed-halide perovskites. Interfacial engineering is a very powerful method to address this issue and passivation agents have been intensively developed, however there is a lack of in-depth understanding regarding the solvent selection during post-treatment. Here, we employed cyclohexylmethylammonium iodide (CMAI) as passivation agent, which is investigated using either isopropanol (IPA) or chloroform (CF) as carrier mediator to study the solvent influence on the stabilization of FAPbI₃. We observed a suppressed-defect perovskite surface toward distinguished composition with 2D CMA₂PbI₄ domain and CMAI domain induced by IPA and CF, respectively. Remarkably, post-treatment with solution of CMAI in CF creates a strain-free environment on the perovskite surface, leading to an improved efficiency of approaching 24% and concurrently an extraordinarily stable α -phase FAPbI₃ PSCs under operation condition, retaining 95% of its initial efficiency after 1050-hour aging. Our resulting device stability is one of the most stable FAPbI₃ based PSCs reported in literature.

1. Introduction

Hybrid organic-inorganic lead halide perovskite solar cells have seen a rapid expansion of research since their first report in 2009, driven by their low-cost solution processing and outstanding optoelectronic properties, leading to high power conversion efficiencies with a record value of 25.5%, the highest efficiency for thin-film solar cells [1–4]. Among various compositions, α -phase FAPbI₃ has recently emerged as the most promising candidate for highly efficient single-junction PSCs, owing to its optimal bandgap, high absorption coefficient, long carrier diffusion length and excellent thermal stability [5–10]. However, its photoactive α -phase (black-phase) is not stable at room temperature and

undergoes a phase transition to the undesired wide-bandgap δ -phase (yellow phase) [5]. Compositional engineering via mixing with methylammonium (MA⁺), cesium (Cs⁺) or bromide (Br⁻) ions has been reported as an effective method to stabilize the α -phase FAPbI₃ [6,11–13]. However, this causes a trade-off by reducing the thermal stability, narrowing absorption spectrum, and introducing phase segregation issues under operational conditions [12,14,15].

Instead, additive engineering has been reported as an effective approach to improve the stability of α -phase FAPbI₃, leading to improved device performance as well as a better long-term stability. For example, several groups reported that methylammonium chloride (MACl) can assist the crystallization and preserve the crystal structure of

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Fig. 1. a) Chemical structure of CMAI. Top-view SEM images of b) pristine perovskite film, c) CMAI (IPA) treated perovskite film, and d) CMAI (CF) treated perovskite film. Surface AFM images of e) pristine perovskite film, f) CMAI (IPA) treated perovskite film, and g) CMAI (CF) treated perovskite film. h) XRD patterns of pristine perovskite film (black), CMAI (IPA) treated perovskite film (red), and CMAI (CF) treated perovskite film (blue). i) Schematic representation of surface reconstruction process after CMAI (IPA) and CMAI (CF) treatment.

α -phase FAPbI₃, thereby providing highly efficient PSCs [8,16]. By optical management and exploiting the absorption spectrum of FAPbI₃, a certified PCE of 23.7% has been reported via introducing 3.8 mol% methylenediammonium dichloride (MDACL₂). Although the bandgap of FAPbI₃ was slightly enlarged, the additive can structurally stabilize the α -phase of FAPbI₃, resulting in a superb operational stability, retaining more than 90% of the initial efficiency after 600 h light soaking [9]. Furthermore, it has been recently found that doping a FAPbI₃ precursor solution with small amount of formamidinium formate (FAFo) can further suppress the non-radiative recombination of charge carriers in the perovskite films by occupying iodide vacancy defects at the perovskite surface as well as the grain boundaries; this enabled a PCE of PSC of 25.6% (certified 25.2%) [10].

In addition to dopant engineering, surface passivation is another important approach for device optimization since non-radiative losses caused by defect states are most commonly located at the perovskite surface [17–21]. Among various passivation agents, isopropyl alcohol (IPA) has become a ubiquitous and default solvent for post-treatment of all kinds of perovskite films, including FAPbI₃ based, mainly due to its ability to dissolve organic ammonium salts and other molecules [22–25]. In particular, it was shown to assist in the anchoring process of organic ammonium salts during the post surface reconstruction [26]. However, exposing the perovskite surface to IPA induces a risk of creating a PbI₂-rich perovskite surface, which generate defects and facilitate perovskite degradation [26,27]. In contrast, low-polarity solvents, such as chloroform (CF), are expected to have less effect on the perovskite surface [28], but have received very little attention so far, mainly due to the limited solubility for the commonly used passivation molecules, such as phenylethylammonium iodide (PEAI) [23], formamidinium halide [29–31], and octylammonium iodide (OAI) [24]. Thus, in this work, we employed interfacial engineering of FAPbI₃ based perovskites by passivation with cyclohexylmethylammonium iodide (CMAI, shown in Fig. 1a), which has been recently reported as an

efficient passivation material through formation of 2D/3D perovskite heterojunction [32,33]. The solubility of CMAI (>30 mg/mL) in a low-polarity solvent, CF, can be significantly improved due to the presence of the cyclohexane group. In addition, we are able to develop an in-depth understanding by comparing the solvent effect of IPA and CF during post-treatment. Importantly, CMAI always has a positive effect on passivating and stabilizing the FAPbI₃ based PSCs regardless which solvent is used. Interestingly, we found the components of both CMAI and 2D perovskite CMA₂PbI₄ were formed on the perovskite surface upon post-treatment, however, with different domain component for different solvents, which stems from the solubility variations of FAI in IPA and CF. This induces target perovskite with a more released residual tension strain and prolonged carrier lifetime with treatment of CMAI in CF compare to CMAI in IPA, resulting in a better device stability of the PSCs under various conditions.

2. Results and discussion

According to the previous work [8], a precursor solution containing FAPbI₃ powder and additional 35 mol% methylammonium chloride (MACl) was used to fabricate black α -phase FAPbI₃ perovskite films. CMAI solution dissolved in IPA or CF (5 mg/mL) was spin-coated onto the perovskite film, without further processing. Here, we use CMAI (IPA) and CMAI (CF) to further refer to solution of CMAI dissolving in IPA and CF, respectively.

To investigate the effect of post-treatment on the perovskite morphology, high-resolution scanning electron microscopy (HR-SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) were carried out. In the SEM images in Fig. 1b–d, a compact pinhole-free polycrystalline film is observed upon treatment of CMAI (IPA), which is quite similar to the control pristine perovskite film; in contrast, a contour-line-like texture appears after post-treating the film with CMAI (CF). Nevertheless, the roughness of CMAI treated films is significantly

Fig. 2. GIXRD peaks with different ψ values of a) the pristine perovskite film (black), b) CMAI (IPA) treated perovskite film, and c) CMAI (CF) treated perovskite film. d) Linear fit of $2\theta \cdot \sin^2\psi$ for the pristine perovskite film (black), CMAI (IPA) treated perovskite film (red), and CMAI (CF) treated perovskite film (blue). e) TRPL of the pristine perovskite film (black), CMAI (IPA) treated perovskite film (red), and CMAI (CF) treated perovskite film (blue). f) XPS N1s core level signals of the pristine perovskite film (black), CMAI (IPA) treated perovskite film (red), and CMAI (CF) treated perovskite film (blue). The two features fitted to the data correspond to FA⁺ and CMA⁺.

reduced regardless of the solvent, as proved by AFM images (Fig. 1e-g). In addition, two new peaks are observed at low 2θ region ($2\theta < 10^\circ$) of the CMAI treated films presented on the XRD patterns shown in Fig. 1h and Fig. S1a. To identify these low-dimensional features, diffractions of CMAI molecule and 2D CMA₂PbI₄ perovskite were investigated, which have diffraction signals located at 5.7° and 5.2° , respectively, as illustrated in Fig. S1b. Interestingly, we found that using IPA, the majority of CMAI molecules become integrated as 2D perovskite, while only a small amount remains unreacted on the surface. In contrary, after treatment with CMAI (CF), the formation of a CMAI dominates, while only a small amount of 2D perovskite is present. We relate this phenomena to the different solubility of the main component, formamidinium iodide (FAI), in the 3D perovskite, which dissolves well in IPA, owing to its high polarity and formation of hydrogen bonding, but shows limited solubility in CF [26,28]. As a result, FAI partially dissolves from the perovskite surface upon exposure to IPA, and is removed during the spin-coating process. The resulting vacancies enable a reaction between the remaining PbI₂ and the newly introduced CMAI which form a 2D perovskite layer, as illustrated in Fig. 1i. In case of exposure to CF, CMAI is limited in its possibility to react with PbI₂ due to the insolubility of FAI in CF. Therefore, such post-treated film is prone to form an additional CMAI layer on top of the perovskite film and we attribute the 2D perovskite phase to the ammonium cation exchange between CMA⁺ and FA⁺. Furthermore, to identify possible solvent effects on our 3D perovskite, we additionally compared grazing incident X-ray diffraction (GIXRD) patterns of films exposed to pure IPA or CF (Fig. S2). A PbI₂ peak, located at 12.6° , is detected on the perovskite surface after IPA treatment, as shown in Fig. S2b. This is consistent with the SEM images shown in Fig. S3a, where plenty of small bright crystals are observed on the perovskite surface exposed to pure IPA, indicating the formation of PbI₂ [30]. However, in comparison with the untreated film, there is no obvious change on the morphology and crystal structure of the perovskite film treated with neat CF, according to the GIXRD pattern and SEM images shown in Fig. S2c and Fig. S3b, suggesting a negligible effect upon CF treatment. To further distinguish the solvent effect, we added 5 mol% PbI₂ into the perovskite precursor solution to form a PbI₂-rich

FAPbI₃ film, where PbI₂ is mainly located on the top of the perovskite film surface, as determined from the GIXRD pattern (Fig. S4) and SEM image (Fig. S5). In this case, only 2D perovskite CMA₂PbI₄ was observed from the GIXRD patterns after the treatment of CMAI (IPA) and CMAI (CF), indicating that CMAI can indeed react with excessive PbI₂ at the surface regardless of solvents. Based on the above results, IPA dissolves and removes the FAI on the perovskite surface, which promotes the formation of 2D CMA₂PbI₄. This is not the case for CF solution treatment, thus the two solvents lead to different surface compositions on top of the perovskite.

The distinguished surface reconstruction processes by CMAI (IPA) and CMAI (CF) resulted in diverse surface composition, which also influenced the residual strain of the perovskite surface and the existence of the intrinsic stress has been recognised as one of critical sources of PSCs instability [34,35]. We focused on the 50 nm region depth of the perovskite film, which is mainly affected by post-treatment, for interfacial strain investigation and employed GIXRD technique with $2\theta \cdot \sin^2\psi$ method for residual stress analysis, where ψ is the instrument tilt angle [36–39]. Due to the high diffraction angle and multiplicative factor of the (012) crystallographic plane, GIXRD patterns at around 31.6° was chosen for the strain distribution analysis. The results are shown in Fig. 2a-c. After the linear fitting of $2\theta \cdot \sin^2\psi$ value by varying ψ , the slope of fitted lines reflects the magnitude of residual strain as well as the strain states [37,38]. As shown in Fig. 2a, the diffraction peaks of the control film gradually shift to smaller 2θ with the increase of ψ from 0° to 50° . The negative slope observed in Fig. 2d indicates that the surface of the pristine perovskite bears a tensile strain. After post-treatment with CMAI (IPA), a reduced shift of the GIXRD peaks vs. ψ (Fig. 2b) is observed, indicating a decreased surface tensile strain after the surface reconstruction process. Notably, a completely strain-free film is obtained upon CMAI (CF) treatment, with a linear slope of $2\theta \cdot \sin^2\psi$ approaching to 0, as observed in Fig. 2c. This implies that the post-treatment of CMAI with a slow cation exchange process in CF plays an important role in releasing the residual tension stress of the perovskite film, which creates a strain-free environment. The release of residual strain contributes to the lattice stabilization of α -FAPbI₃, which

Fig. 3. a) Device architecture of the PSC. b) IPCE and integrated J_{sc} of control device (black), CMAI (IPA) treated device (red) and CMAI (CF) treated device (blue). c) J-V curves of the best control device (black), CMAI (IPA) treated device (red) and CMAI (CF) treated device (blue) under reverse scan (RS). d) Power output of the control device (black), CMAI (IPA) treated device (red) and CMAI (CF) treated device (blue) at MPPT. e) V_{oc} versus logarithm of light intensity of the control device (black), CMAI (IPA) treated device (red) and CMAI (CF) treated device (blue). f) J-V curves of the champion 1 cm^2 device, inset image is the picture of large area PSC device.

can consequently lead to a significant enhancement on the device stability (see discussion below). Moreover, it is well known that the existence of residual strain will also influence defect concentration and non-radiative recombination of perovskite films [38–40]. Therefore, time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) measurements were carried out to further examine the difference induced by the two solvents. As shown in Fig. 2e, compared to the control film, both CMAI-treated perovskite films present slower photoluminescence decay, especially the one exposed to CF shows the longest lifetime. This indicates that the introduction of CMAI could efficiently reduce the defect density and suppress the non-radiative recombination of the perovskite film [10,39]. To further evaluate the solvent effect on film trap density, space-charge-limited-current (SCLC) measurements were carried out on electron-only devices with structure of FTO/cp-TiO₂/mp-TiO₂/FAPbI₃/CMAI/PCBM/Au, as shown in Fig. S6a. The control device shows a trap-filling limited voltage (V_{TFL}) of 0.423 V, which reduced to 0.330 V and 0.307 V after post-treatment with CMAI (IPA) and CMAI (CF), respectively (Fig. S6b-d). Correspondingly, the calculated trap density (N_t) decreases from $8.08 \times 10^{15}\text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $6.30 \times 10^{15}\text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $5.86 \times 10^{15}\text{ cm}^{-3}$ upon the CMAI treatment, which is estimated by the following equation: $V_{TFL} = (eN_t L^2)/(2\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r)$, where e is the elementary charge, L is the thickness of FAPbI₃ perovskite film (600 nm), ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, and ϵ_r is the relative dielectric constant [41]. The reduced trap density indicates the formation of an effective passivation layer after surface reconstruction, which could improve the photovoltaic performances [30,42].

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted to investigate the element composition after the surface reconstruction, as illustrated in Fig. S7 and Fig. 2f. The Pb 4f_{7/2} core level signal was located at 138.56 eV in the pristine film, however shifted towards a slightly higher bonding energy in both cases upon CMAI treatment, suggesting the variation of surface chemical environment. From the pristine film, N1s peak of FA⁺ was located at 400.5 eV and no MA⁺ peak (402.1 eV) was found [43], which is in agreement with the pure FAPbI₃ film composition [8]. After passivation treatment with CMAI regardless of the solvent, a new N 1s peak appeared at 402.1 eV and the intensity of FA⁺

Table 1

Photovoltaic parameters and hysteresis index (HI) of control, CMAI (IPA), CMAI (CF) treated champion devices.

	Scan direction	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	FF	PCE (%)	Hysteresis index (HI) (%) ^c
Control	RS ^a	25.69	1.092	0.763	21.40	3.3
Control	FS ^b	25.66	1.084	0.744	20.69	
CMAI-IPA	RS	25.76	1.145	0.806	23.77	1.6
CMAI-IPA	FS	25.65	1.142	0.799	23.40	
CMAI-CF	RS	25.75	1.149	0.809	23.94	1.1
CMAI-CF	FS	25.70	1.147	0.803	23.67	

a) Reverse scan; b) Forward scan; c) HI = $(PCE_{RS} - PCE_{FS})/PCE_{RS}$

peak was significantly reduced, implying that a new layer dominated by CMAI was formed on top of the 3D perovskite film. Notably, the ratios between CMAI⁺ and FAI⁺, calculated from the simulative integrated areas of the two N1s peaks were 6.22 and 4.59 via CMAI (IPA) and CMAI (CF) treatment, respectively. Such reduction in cation ratio is another evidence showing that IPA could remove more FAI from the perovskite surface, thus resulting in a lower concentration of FAI during the surface reconstruction process.

PSCs based on FTO glass/cp-TiO₂/mp-TiO₂/3D perovskite/passivation layer/spiro-MeOTAD/Au were fabricated to evaluate the photovoltaic performance upon post-treatment by CMAI. The device architecture is shown in Fig. 3a and the cross-sectional SEM images of the devices are illustrated in Fig. S8. Reverse-scanned (RS) and forward-scanned (FS) J-V curves of the devices were measured under simulated sunlight of air mass (AM) 1.5G. Comparable improvements are observed with CMAI treatment using the two solvents, in comparison to the control device. The average values of photovoltaic parameters are summarized in Table S1. It is observed that the concentration of 5 mg/mL CMAI in either IPA or CF delivers the best device performance. The

Fig. 4. a) Contact angle of water droplet on perovskite film with and without CMAI treatment. b) Shelf stability of control devices (black), CMAI (IPA) treated devices (red) and CMAI (CF) treated devices (blue) under relative humidity of 20–30%, five devices for each condition. c) Long-term stability of control device (black), CMAI (IPA) treated device (red) and CMAI (CF) treated device (blue) under constant simulated one-sun illumination in N_2 atmosphere at room temperature. d) Shelf stability of control devices (black), CMAI (IPA) treated devices (red) and CMAI (CF) treated devices (blue) under relative humidity of $40 \pm 10\%$ at $50^\circ C$, four devices for each condition.

enhanced performance induced by CMAI treatment can be attributed to the dramatic increase in open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) and fill factor (FF), leading to an average power conversion efficiency (PCE) of the passivated devices of over 23%. The photocurrent density (J_{sc}) of the target devices show negligible differences to the control devices, which is in agreement with the comparable incident photo-to-current efficiency (IPCE) and integrated photocurrent density shown in Fig. 3b. The champion performance with and without CMAI treatment is summarized in Table 1 and illustrated in Fig. 3c. The best PCE with CMAI (IPA) treatment is 23.77% with a J_{sc} of 25.76 mA/cm^2 , a V_{OC} of 1.145 V, and a FF of 0.806. The CMAI (CF) treated champion device shows a PCE of 23.94%, with a J_{sc} of 25.75 mA/cm^2 , a V_{OC} of 1.149 V, and a FF of 0.809, with reduced hysteresis. The stabilized power output of the champion devices was analysed by maximum power point tracking (MPPT) under ambient air with relevant humidity of 30%. The stabilized PCE of both passivated devices exhibit over 23.5% after 10 min aging and the control device is at 21.0%. In addition, as shown in Fig. S9, the statistics of photovoltaic parameters distribution (20 devices for each condition) shows good reproducibility upon CMAI treatment. It is worth noticing that as shown in Table S1, both V_{OC} and FF of the post-treated devices show only slight improvement upon formation of pure 2D interlayer by heating the as-prepared passivated perovskite film [33]. This suggests that in our system, without further annealing, an interlayer with moieties of both 2D perovskite and CMAI play an important role in passivating the 3D perovskite surface. Furthermore, the calculated ideality factor (n_{id}) of control, CMAI (IPA), and CMAI (CF) treated devices are 1.64, 1.36, and 1.30, respectively. The reduced n_{id} confirms a significantly suppressed trap-assisted recombination via CMAI passivation, which accordingly resulted in an enhancement in V_{OC} [44]. Encouraged by the excellent results above, large area (1 cm^2) devices were fabricated to evaluate the practicability of the passivation strategy. As shown in Fig. 3f, one of the best PCE of the target device is 21.07%, with a J_{sc} of 25.75 mA/cm^2 , a V_{OC} of 1.154 V and a FF of 0.709.

Except for the excellent device performance, solvent effect on device stability has also been assessed. Firstly, the contact angle of water droplets on the perovskite films with and without passivation layer were measured. As shown in Fig. 4a, a dramatic improvement of hydrophobicity after CMAI treatment is observed compared to the pristine

perovskite films; the contact angles increase from 57° to around 90° . We first exposed the perovskite films in ambient condition with relative humidity of $40 \pm 20\%$ for 15 days and monitored the phase stability by GIXRD, as shown in Fig. S10. A pronounced δ -phase $FAPbI_3$ at 11.7° is clearly observed from the pristine perovskite film, indicating a significant phase transformation. In sharp contrast, both CMAI (IPA) and CMAI (CF) treated perovskite films show negligible δ -phase under the same condition, especially the one treated by CMAI (CF), suggesting an outstanding phase stability upon passivation treatment. To further investigate the device shelf stability, we subjected unencapsulated devices to air with a relative humidity of 20–30% in the dark. As illustrated in Fig. 4b, the PCE of target devices after 100-day storage retain 95% and 91% after post-treatment with CMAI (CF) and CMAI (IPA), respectively. In contrast, the control devices show more than 15% decrease under the same condition. In addition, we also tested the devices under MPPT at a constant one-sun illumination in N_2 atmosphere at room temperature. As shown in Fig. 4c, the PCE of the control device drops by almost 24% of its initial value after 1050 h aging. In sharp contrast, both CMAI passivated devices retain more 90% of the initial PCE value. In particular, the CMAI (CF) treated device shows only 5% normalized PCE loss, and is therefore comparably more stable than the device treated with CMAI (IPA). It is worth noting that our resulting device is one of the most stable PSCs based on $FAPbI_3$ in current literatures, as summarized in Table S2. Furthermore, we subjected the unencapsulated devices to $50^\circ C$ with humidity at $40 \pm 10\%$ to investigate their stability upon elevated temperature and humidity for 500 h. As expected, CMAI (CF) treated devices retain 93% of their initial PCE, about 27% PCE loss is observed from the CMAI (IPA) treated devices, whereas the control devices show almost 60% PCE loss. We attribute this further enhanced stability to the more released residual strain induced by CMAI (CF).

3. Conclusion

Overall, we successfully stabilized the α -phase of $FAPbI_3$ based PSCs through interfacial engineering with CMAI. More importantly, our in-depth optoelectronic film together with device characterizations unraveled the rules of CMAI as passivation agent on reducing non-radiative recombination and the solvent as mediator on leasing

surface residual strains during the post-treatment process. Our work paves a way on optimizing the PSCs more comprehensively and sheds light on the detrimental role of the solvent selection for post-treatment process according to the system of the 3D perovskite and passivation molecule.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jiajia Suo: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Measurement, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Bowen Yang:** Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Measurement, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Jaeki Jeong:** Methodology. **Tiankai Zhang:** Measurement. **Selina Olthof:** Measurement. **Feng Gao:** Visualization. **Michael Grätzel:** Visualization. **Gerrit Boschloo:** Visualization. **Anders Hagfeldt:** Resources, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Author contributions

J. S and B. Y. contributed equally to this work. B. Y. and J. S. conceived the idea, prepared films, fabricated all devices and analyzed the characterizations and wrote the manuscript. T. Z. assisted in AFM measurements. S. O. performed the XPS measurements. A. H. directed the overall research. All authors read and commented on the manuscript.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.nanoen.2022.106924](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2022.106924).

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